

Amines as Vapour Phase Corrosion Inhibitors for 3S Aluminium in Vapours of Hydrochloric Acid

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An attempt has been made to study the inhibitor action of some amines towards 3S aluminium in HCl vapours. Pyridine and ethanolamines are found very effective as vapour phase inhibitors.

THE studies on inhibition due to volatile compounds is of recent origin. So far most of the work is confined to the inhibition of steel; little attention been paid towards inhibition of aluminium, an alloy of great industrial importance.

Vapour phase corrosion inhibitors are very similar to the organic adsorption type inhibitors and may possess very high vapour pressure. Consequently, such compounds can be used to inhibit atmospheric corrosion of metals without being placed in direct contact with the metal surface. If such inhibitors are placed in the vicinity of metal to be protected, they are transferred to the metal surface by sublimation and condensation. The vapour phase inhibitors are usually only effective if used in closed spaces such as inside package or on the interior machinery during shipment.¹

Plant operations of vast magnitude are dependent upon successful application of corrosion inhibitors. The use of corrosion inhibitors has been tremendous for the last few years.

Accurate methods for the study of inhibitor action in the vapour phase has been given by Mindorach² and Volrabona³. Various amines and salts of cyclic amines among which the best known is dicyclohexyl nitrite are of great interest⁴⁻⁵. In the present investigation an attempt has been made to study the inhibitive powers of some amines on corrosion of aluminium by vapours of hydrochloric acid.

Experimental

For weight loss data coupons of 3S aluminium of size 6×3 cm (22 S.W.C.) were used. They had the following composition :

Cu, 0.15; Mn, 1.5; Fe, 0.75; Si, 0.6; Zn, 0.10, the remainder being aluminium. All the chemicals used were of B.D.H. (C.P. grade). Preparation and cleaning procedures for the specimen adopted was that described by Champion⁶.

In hydrochloric acid vapours, the plates were hung by means of rubber strip in polythene boxes whose dimensions were of the order of 9"×5.5"×5.5". 250 ml of 10*N* HCl and 100 ml of inhibitors were kept

in separate beakers on the extreme sides of the polythene boxes. The experiment was carried out at the atmospheric pressure. A hole of the size of 5 mm diameter was made at the centre of the lid of the box.

Two plates of aluminium were hung just near the corrosive medium (below orifice) and the other two plates were placed just above the inhibitor, both being placed at the extreme sides of the container. For each experiment two plates were used and average values were taken into consideration. The reproducibility of the results were $\pm 2\%$. The whole experiment was carried out at room temperature. Maximum and minimum temperature range was 35° to 23° respectively. The relative humidity variation was 60±5%. The weight loss data has been shown in Table 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—INHIBITION OF 3S ALUMINIUM IN VAPOURS OF HYDROCHLORIC ACID

Duration : 45 days.

(Wt. loss data of 3S aluminium specimens near to the corrosive media and near to the orifice).

Inhibitors	Wt. loss in mgm.	Mdd	Percentage inhibition
Blank	2.5162	155.3	—
Aniline	1.3399	82.7	47.0
Dimethylamine	1.6879	104.2	33.0
Diethylamine	2.3958	147.3	5.0
N : N-diethylamine	1.6236	100.3	35.0
Ethanolamine	0.6434	39.6	75.0
Triethanolamine	1.4847	91.6	41.0
Pyridine	0.6080	31.3	80.0

Observation

Experiment showed that corrosion was high at the bottom of the plates. It seemed that hydrochloric acid vapours condensed on the plate and accumulated at the lower parts of the plates resulting in severe corrosion. In case of aniline and triethanol amine there appeared to be direct reaction.

TABLE 2—WT. LOSS DATA OF 3S ALUMINIUM SPECIMENS, FAR FROM THE ORIFICE AND NEAR TO THE INHIBITING MEDIUM

Inhibitors	Wt. loss in mgm.	Duration : 45 days	
		Mdd	Percentage inhibition
Blank	2.1930	135.4	—
Aniline	1.2072	74.5	45.0
Dimethylamine	1.3103	80.8	40.0
Diethylamine	2.0000	123.4	9.0
N : N-Diethylamine	1.3232	82.3	39.0
Ethanolamine	0.3352	20.7	85.0
Triethanolamine	0.9920	61.2	55.0
Pyridine	0.2520	15.6	88.0

Consequently the salt deposit was observed in the beaker containing inhibitor.

Amines formed a sticky, semisolid mass, on the aluminium plates, the thickness of which was about one centimeter. This formed a protective layer which prevented further corrosion. In case of pyridine an invisible film was formed which acted as barrier in the corrosion process. The nature of corrosion was of the pitting type.

Results

Hydrochloric acid vapours are highly corrosive to aluminium, the weight loss being as high as 2.5 g with a single specimen. Vapours of amines exhibit variable inhibitive powers towards corrosion of aluminium. The approximate order of the increasing inhibitive power of the amines is as follows :

Diethanolamine < Dimethylamine < N : N diethylamine triethanolamine < Aniline < Ethanolamine < Pyridine. The highest and lowest inhibition exhibited by the amines are 5.2 and 88.4%. The corrosion loss is somewhat higher and inhibition is somewhat low when the specimens are placed just near to the corrosive medium and below the orifice in the vessel in which the experiment was carried out.

Discussion

The specimens kept nearer to the corrosive medium and just below orifice show quite high corrosion rates than those kept above the inhibitor medium. The percentage inhibition in the former cases are also somewhat low. This effect appears primarily due to air (in reality the oxygen) which might diffuse through the orifice, the local concentration of oxygen at the plates near to the orifice will be invariably high, leading to some depolarization of the local cathodes.

The inhibition by nitrogen containing substance is primarily due to the adsorption of these compounds at the surface of the metal. Greater the adsorption, greater should be the inhibition. The adsorption takes through the nitrogen atom—a key atom, of the amines, greater the electron density over the nitrogen atom, greater is the adsorption. This criteria does

not seem to be quite justified for the vapour phase inhibitor. The pk_b values of the amines are given in Table 3. Higher pk_b values indicate low electron

TABLE 3—BOILING POINTS AND pk_b VALUES OF THE INHIBITOR STUDIES

Inhibitors	Boiling point °C	pk_b
Diethylamine	55	3.07
Dimethylamine	7.5	3.23
N : N-diethylamine	216	9.62
Triethanolamine	360	7.76
Aniline	184	9.38
Ethanolamine	170	9.50
Pyridine	115	8.96

density over the nitrogen atom. Pyridine has quite high pk_b value while diethylamine has quite low pk_b value which is not reflected in their respective inhibitive powers. Dimethylamine and N : N diethylamine exhibit nearly equal inhibition even when their pk_b values differ greatly.

Diethylamine (55°) and dimethylamine (7.5°) have quite low boiling points as compared to those of N : N diethylamine (216°) and Triethanolamine (360°), while the boiling point of aniline (184°), ethanolamine (170°) and pyridine (115°) are quite intermediate. Higher the boiling points lower will be their concentration in the vapours leading to low inhibition. Diethylamine and dimethylamine will have quite high concentration in vapours and therefore should show high inhibition. However, due to their high volatility, they will be exhausted soon and therefore will not be available throughout the exposure period. Those having intermediate boiling points will have quite moderate concentration in the vapours and will persist for a considerable period showing high inhibition. It is evident from above that the continuous supply of vapours of an inhibitor is quite essential for high inhibition.

References

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